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Appendix S1

Contents

1. ODMAP protocol	1
2. Spatial filtering	6
3. Feature selection - Log Loss	8
4. Benchmarking pipeline	9
5. Hyperparameter tuning - search space	10
6. Model output	11
7. Variable importance per base model	12
8. Performance metrics per model and species	20
References	22

1 ODMAP protocol

Table S1 shows relevant information for this study according to the ODMAP protocol suggested by Zurell et al. (2020). More details on target species, data sources, preprocessing operations and packages used are provided.

Table S1: ODMAP protocol

<i>ODMAP element</i>	Contents
OVERVIEW	
<i>Authorship</i>	Authors: Carmelo Bonannella, Tomislav Hengl, Johannes Heisig, Leandro Parente, Marvin N Wright, Martin Herold, Sytze de Bruin Contact email: carmelo.bonannella@opengeohub.org Title: Forest tree species distribution for Europe 2000–2020: mapping potential and realized distributions using spatiotemporal Machine Learning DOI:
<i>Model objective</i>	Objective: Mapping/interpolation Target outputs continuous occurrence probabilities of potential and actual presence
<i>Taxon</i>	16 tree species native/commonly found in Mediterranean, temperate or boreal forests in Europe
<i>Location</i>	Europe
<i>Scale of analysis</i>	Spatial extent (Lon/Lat: Longitude -48.52° E, 60.65° E, Latitude 26.77° N, 72.02° N Spatial resolution: 30 m x 30 m Temporal resolution and extent: we modelled a single time slice for all potential distributions (2018–2020). We split the a 20 years time period (2000–2020) in 6 time slices (2000–2002, 2002–2006, 2006–2010, 2010–2014, 2014–2018 and 2018–2020) for realized distributions.

	Type of extent boundary: rectangular
<i>Biodiversity data overview</i>	Observation type: standardised monitoring and volunteer-based surveys Response/Data type: presence/absence data
<i>Type of predictors</i>	Climatic, topographic, lithological, hydrological, vegetation (binary species distribution maps of other tree species), remotely sensed (spectral reflectance)
<i>Conceptual model / Hypotheses</i>	We modelled realized distribution using environmental and remotely sensed variables, while we used only environmental variables for potential distribution. We wanted to test the influence of (i) remotely sensed and (ii) high resolution variables on predictive performances of realized distribution.
<i>Assumptions</i>	We assumed that species are at pseudo-equilibrium with the environment. We assumed that distribution maps of other tree species could be used as a proxy for interspecific interactions. Probability of presence is relative to the mapped target species, irrespective of the potential co-occurrence of other species in the same 30 m pixel and should not be confused with the absolute abundance or proportion of each species in the pixel area. The sum of the presence probabilities of different species in the same pixel can thus exceed 100 %
<i>SDM algorithms</i>	Algorithms: The final SDMs were fitted using three different algorithms: generalised linear models (GLM) with Lasso regularization, gradient boosted trees (GBT), and random forests (RF). Model complexity: We chose different modelling parameters to optimise each algorithm. Model settings were chosen to yield intermediately complex response surfaces but prevent excessive overfitting. Ensembles: The results from the three learners were combined in an ensemble model based on stacked generalization. We used logistic regression with Lasso regularization as ensemble model.
<i>Model workflow</i>	Hyperparameter tuning was conducted for all models on a a random 25% subset of observations. We evaluated each combination of hyperparameters by comparing logarithmic loss values during a 5-fold spatial cross validation replicated 5 times. Models were then fitted on the entire training dataset using the best (lowest logloss) combination of hyperparameters. Probability values obtained from the three models were then used to train the meta-learner. 5-fold spatial cross validation was used for the level 0 models. The out-of-fold predictions were used to build a level 1 training dataset for the meta-learner.
<i>Software, codes and data</i>	Software: All analyses were conducted using R version 4.1.1 (R Core Team, 2021) with packages caret (Kuhn, 2021), data.table (Dowle and Srinivasan, 2021), dplyr (Wickham et al., 2021), minio.s3 (Leeper, 2017), mlr (Bischl et al., 2016), rgdal (Bivand et al., 2021), sf (Pebesma, 2018), sp (Pebesma and Bivand, 2005), spThin (Aiello-Lammens et al., 2015), stringr (Wickham, 2019), terra (Hijmans, 2021) and custom functions and Python version 3.8.6 (Van Rossum and Drake, 2009) with packages matplotlib (Hunter, 2007), numpy (Harris et al., 2020), pandas (McKinney et al., 2010) and scikit-learn (Pedregosa et al., 2011). Code availability: All codes are available on GitLab (https://gitlab.com/geoharmonizer_inea/spatial-layers/-/tree/master/veg_mapping) Data availability: All data is available through Zenodo (Bonannella et al., 2022)
DATA	
<i>Biodiversity data</i>	Taxon names: Abies alba Mill., Castanea sativa Mill., Corylus avellana L., Fagus sylvatica L., Olea europaea L., Picea abies L. H. Karst., Pinus halepensis Mill., Pinus nigra J. F. Arnold, Pinus pinea L., Pinus sylvestris L., Prunus avium L., Quercus cerris L., Quercus ilex L., Quercus robur L., Quercus suber L., Salix caprea L. Details on taxonomic reference system: standard biologic taxonomy

	<p>Ecological level: individual</p> <p>Biodiversity data source: Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), EU-Forest (Mauri et al., 2017), LUCAS (EUROSTAT, 2017)</p> <p>Sampling design: uniform (EU-Forest, LUCAS) or unknown (GBIF); latest instance in case of multi-temporal observations</p> <p>Sample size per taxon: <i>Abies alba</i> Mill. (), <i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill. (), <i>Corylus avellana</i> L. (), <i>Fagus sylvatica</i> L. (), <i>Olea europaea</i> L. (), <i>Picea abies</i> L. H. Karst. (), <i>Pinus halepensis</i> Mill. (), <i>Pinus nigra</i> J. F. Arnold (), <i>Pinus pinea</i> L. (), <i>Pinus sylvestris</i> L. (), <i>Prunus avium</i> L. (), <i>Quercus cerris</i> L. (), <i>Quercus ilex</i> L. (), <i>Quercus robur</i> L. (), <i>Quercus suber</i> L. (), <i>Salix caprea</i> L. ()</p> <p>Country mask: European Union, Iceland, Norway and Switzerland</p> <p>Data cleaning/filtering: Point locations were filtered using a high-resolution land mask for Europe and by leveraging existing quality flags indicating serious location issues. A second filtering step involved the usage of yearly high-resolution forest masks. To overcome the uneven sampling intensity and potential point clustering, we applied an additional spatial filter to the presence points using the <i>spThin</i> R package. A distance of 2 km was considered as minimum distance between the points, to harmonize the sampling intensity between presence and absence data. The procedure was repeated 10 times: at each iteration, the algorithm randomly removes one observation from the dataset until no observation is left with a nearest neighbor closer than the thinning distance. Among the 10 datasets obtained, the one with the largest number of records was retained and used for modeling.</p> <p>Absence data: We used the land cover points from LUCAS database as absence data. All land cover classes except class C (woodland) were used as absence data for realized distribution, while for potential distribution points belonging to class A (artificial land) and class B (cropland) were also excluded. Other tree species presence locations were also used as absence data: these points were first overlaid with a chorological map of the target species and only the ones falling outside the species range were then used as absence.</p> <p>Potential biases: Spatial observation density for presence data varies greatly throughout the study area and across different species resulting in over- or underrepresented areas.</p>
<i>Data partitioning</i>	<p>A 5-fold spatial cross validation was used to partition the data for model fitting. Predictive performances were assessed using a 5-fold spatial cross validation repeated 5 times. Spatial allocation for the points was conducted using spatial blocking with a blocking factor of 30 km.</p>
<i>Predictor variables</i>	<p>Predictor variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Climate:</i> 19 bioclimatic predictors, solar direct and diffuse irradiation, 13 cloud fraction layers, 12 snow probability layers, 12 water vapor pressure layers, 12 wind speed layers, time series of precipitation, monthly time series of surface temperature (minimum, average, maximum), monthly time series of air temperature (minimum, average, maximum) • <i>Topography:</i> elevation, slope, aspect, positive and negative openness, eastness and northness, hillshade • <i>Hydrology:</i> surface water occurrence, height above nearest drainage (HAND), flow accumulation area and long-term flood hazard map • <i>Vegetation:</i> 50 chorological tree species maps • <i>Remotely sensed:</i> 7 seasonal time series of Landsat bands (blue, green, red, NIR, SWIR1, SWIR2 and thermal), 7 seasonal time series of spectral indices (EVI, EVI2, MSAVI, NBR, NDVI, NDWI, SAVI), long term bare ground cover. <p>Data sources:</p>

•*Climate*: bioclimatic predictors were downloaded from <https://chelsea-climate.org/bioclim>, solar direct and diffuse irradiation from <https://globalsolaratlas.info/download>, 13 cloud fraction layers from <https://www.earthenv.org/cloud>, 12 snow probability layers from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5774953>, 12 water vapor pressure layers from <http://www.worldclim.com/version2>, 12 wind speed layers from <https://www.climatologylab.org/terraclimate.html>, time series of precipitation, monthly time series of surface temperature (minimum, average, maximum), monthly time series of air temperature (minimum, average, maximum) were downloaded and reprocessed from reprocessed Copernicus ERA5 data (<https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.bd0915c6>)

•*Topography*: elevation, slope, aspect and hillshade were downloaded from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4724549>, positive and negative openness, eastness and northness from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4486135>

•*Hydrology*: surface water occurrence was obtained from <https://global-surface-water.appspot.com/>, height above nearest drainage (HAND) and flow accumulation area from http://hydro.iis.u-tokyo.ac.jp/~yamada/MERIT_Hydro/ and long-term flood hazard map from Dottori et al. (2016)

•*Vegetation*: 50 chorological tree species maps were downloaded from <https://forest.jrc.ec.europa.eu/en/european-atlas/atlas-data-and-metadata/>

•*Remotely sensed*: time series of Landsat bands were downloaded from <https://glad.umd.edu/ard/landsat-ard-download> and the spectral indices were derived from them; the long term bare ground cover was downloaded from <https://glad.umd.edu/dataset/global-2010-bare-ground-30-m>

Spatial resolution and spatial extent of raw data: Original resolution of raw data goes from 5 km to 30 m. Data were collected and overlaid with the points at their original resolution and then resampled at 30 m resolution for map production. Data with global coverage were clipped at the spatial extent of the scale of analysis.

Map projection: All layers were reprojected in EPSG:3035 coordinate reference system

Temporal resolution and temporal extent of raw data: Data with long-term aggregates or considered as not changing for the temporal scale of the analysis (i.e. elevation) were treated as static variables. The long-term aggregates cover the period 1979–2013 (bioclimatic layers) or 2000–2016 (cloud fraction, snow probability, water vapor). Landsat data and derived spectral indices cover the period 1999–2020, with a temporal resolution of 16 days. Time series of precipitation, surface temperature and air temperature cover the period 2000–2020 with a hourly temporal resolution.

	<p>Data preprocessing: Cloud and cloud shadow pixels were removed from Landsat images, maintaining only the quality assessment-QA values labeled as clear-sky. Individual images were averaged by season according to three different quantiles (25th, 50th and 75th) and the following calendar dates for all period: winter (December 2 of previous year until March 20 of current year), spring (March 21 until June 24 of current year), summer (June 25 until September 12 of current year) fall (September 13 until December 1 of current year). Missing values were imputed using the <i>Temporal Moving Window Median</i> algorithm. Spectral indices were computed for each year and season using the 50th quantile only. Time series of precipitation, surface temperature and air temperature were aggregated on a monthly scale. The following steps were used for temperature data: (i) aggregate CHELSA to ERA5 spatial resolution, (ii) calculate difference between ERA5 Land and aggregated CHELSA, (iii) interpolate differences with a Gaussian filter to 30 arc seconds and (iv) add the interpolated differences to CHELSA. A different approach was used for precipitation, with proportions instead of differences: using proportions ensures that areas without recorded precipitation remain areas without precipitation; only in the case of actual precipitation in a given area, precipitation was redistributed according to the spatial detail of CHELSA: aggregate CHELSA to ERA5 spatial resolution, calculate proportion between ERA5 Land and aggregated CHELSA, interpolate proportion with a Gaussian filter to 30 arc seconds, multiply the interpolated proportion with CHELSA.</p>
MODEL	
<i>Multicollinearity</i>	Collinearity analysis was not conducted.
<i>Model settings</i>	Model settings: Grid search with a 5 step was used to conduct hyperparameter tuning. Hyperparameters used in the final models change based on the species and the distribution type. Common settings across all models was the "probability" mode, to have a probabilistic (0–100) output for presence and absence. Spatial 5-fold cross validation was used in the inner loop (training of the three component models for the ensemble) and in the outer loop (training of the meta-learner). All random forests model were trained with the same number of trees ($n_{tree} = 85$) due to computational constraints. All GLM models used in the final model were fitted with the λ_{min} . Lasso regularization was used for the GLM component model and for the meta-learner (logistic regression).
<i>Model estimates</i>	We did not analyzed the coefficients of the meta-learner in depth.
<i>Model selection / Model averaging / Ensembles</i>	We used an ensemble model based on stacked generalization (Wolpert, 1992). Outputs made by the component models are the input of a meta-learner which then produces the final prediction.
<i>Non-independence correction/analyses</i>	None
<i>Threshold selection</i>	None
ASSESSMENT	
<i>Performance statistics</i>	Predictive model performance on validation data (based on the 5-fold spatial block cross-validation repeated 5 times) was assessed using two different performance measures: area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) and logarithmic loss (log loss)
<i>Plausibility check</i>	Produced maps were compared with distribution maps from European Atlas of Forest Tree Species.
PREDICTION	
<i>Prediction output</i>	Prediction unit: We used continuous predictions of occurrence probability per species.

<i>Uncertainty quantification</i>	Uncertainty for the final ensemble model was accounted as the standard deviation of the predicted probabilities of the base learners. The principle is that the higher the standard deviation the more uncertain the model is towards the right value to assign to the pixel.
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2 Spatial filtering

Table S2 shows the number of presence points before and after the thinning operation. The spatial thinning was conducted using the *spThin* package (Aiello-Lammens et al., 2015). A distance of 2 km was considered as minimum distance between the points, to harmonize the sampling intensity between presence and absence data. The procedure was repeated 10 times. Among the 10 datasets obtained, the one with the largest number of records was retained and used for modeling. Due to computational constraints, we first overlaid the points with a 10 x 10 km grid and ran the thinning procedure per tile. Figure S1 shows the spatial distribution of presence points per species after the spatial thinning operation.

Table S2: Number of presence points before and after the thinning operation.

Species	Distribution	Presence	Absence	Presence thinned	Absence thinned	Prevalence	Prevalence thinned
<i>A. alba</i>	Potential	45422	793484	38622	264833	0.05	0.15
<i>C. sativa</i>	Potential	77363	796588	35068	327986	0.09	0.11
<i>C. avellana</i>	Potential	32134	533362	28436	120445	0.06	0.24
<i>F. sylvatica</i>	Potential	197107	750752	147655	240030	0.26	0.62
<i>O. europaea</i>	Potential	50656	667416	5794	418689	0.07	0.01
<i>P. abies</i>	Potential	360112	820472	284594	270365	0.44	1.10
<i>P. halepensis</i>	Potential	233961	916627	41758	446998	0.26	0.09
<i>P. nigra</i>	Potential	139497	1091032	29711	467060	0.13	0.064
<i>P. pinea</i>	Potential	239254	853945	19314	464513	0.28	0.042
<i>P. sylvestris</i>	Potential	507664	763571	283882	279289	0.66	1.00
<i>P. avium</i>	Potential	22852	575044	21616	184178	0.04	0.12
<i>Q. cerris</i>	Potential	13774	1106501	13072	450317	0.01	0.03
<i>Q. ilex</i>	Potential	57213	1045184	36294	422799	0.05	0.09
<i>Q. robur</i>	Potential	113044	655526	97113	181057	0.17	0.54
<i>Q. suber</i>	Potential	419975	840378	12877	454942	0.5	0.03
<i>S. caprea</i>	Potential	45753	488610	42544	75030	0.094	0.57
<i>A. alba</i>	Realized	45422	1240411	32144	455595	0.037	0.07
<i>C. sativa</i>	Realized	77363	1215288	29985	528953	0.064	0.06
<i>C. avellana</i>	Realized	32134	1044035	22919	383698	0.031	0.06
<i>F. sylvatica</i>	Realized	197107	1196053	128325	457652	0.16	0.28
<i>O. europaea</i>	Realized	50656	1019575	5249	597376	0.05	0.01
<i>P. abies</i>	Realized	360112	1207099	260011	448564	0.3	0.58
<i>P. halepensis</i>	Realized	233961	1261372	36844	598154	0.19	0.06
<i>P. nigra</i>	Realized	139497	1425066	28380	608094	0.098	0.05
<i>P. pinea</i>	Realized	239254	1192136	17181	615999	0.2	0.03
<i>P. sylvestris</i>	Realized	507664	1178176	239508	427508	0.43	0.56
<i>P. avium</i>	Realized	22852	1058215	17093	430548	0.022	0.04
<i>Q. cerris</i>	Realized	13774	1455524	11536	602902	0.0095	0.02
<i>Q. ilex</i>	Realized	57213	1401501	32826	580366	0.041	0.06
<i>Q. robur</i>	Realized	113044	1156574	76487	433485	0.098	0.18
<i>Q. suber</i>	Realized	419975	1188462	12538	610216	0.35	0.02
<i>S. caprea</i>	Realized	45753	1007707	36704	342866	0.045	0.11

Figure S1: Distribution of presence points per species after thinning. Absence points are omitted for visualization purposes.

3 Feature selection - Log Loss

Figure S2 describes the output of the Recursive Feature Elimination algorithm: a random forests model is fitted initially with all the predictors in the dataset. The least important features (in our methodology, the last 10 features for each iteration) are then removed and a new model is refitted until a minimum number is reached (in our methodology, the last model is fitted with only 10 features). The number of features selected in our methodology is the minimum of the function, which retains the highest number of features and the lowest logloss value (330 in figure).

Figure S2: Log Loss performances by number of selected features.

4 Benchmarking pipeline

Fig. S3 shows a specific part of the workflow for the study, specifically the feature selection and hyperparameter tuning part. This workflow was first used to select which set of predictors and algorithms would maximize predictive performances on a 25% random subsample. After the best algorithms were identified, the workflow was ran once again on the whole dataset to produce the final models used for the predictions.

Figure S3: Example workflow illustrating the feature selection and benchmarking process for one species

5 Hyperparameter tuning - search space

Table S3 shows the complete search space used for all the algorithms tested in the paper. In light gray the name of the R package used to implement the algorithm is reported, in brackets the name of the algorithm. p refers to the number of predictor variables, while columns *Lower* and *Upper* indicate the bounds of the regions in the hyperparameter space. Due to computational constraints, we set the *num.trees* parameter for Random forest to 85. The tested activation functions for the neural network were *sigmoid* and *tanh*, while for the output we tested both *sigmoid* and *softmax*. For GLM we used the automatically generated λ sequence and selected the λ_{\min} .

Table S3: Hyperparameter space for the analyzed algorithms.

Algorithm	Hyperparameter	Type	Lower	Upper
C5.0				
(Classification trees)	minCases	integer	0	10
	CF	numeric	0	0.5
kknn				
(k-nearest neighbor)	k	integer	1	50
deepnet				
(Artificial neural network)	learning rate	numeric	0.0001	0.00001
	numepochs	integer	10	20
	batchsize	integer	50	150
	hidden_dropout	numeric	0.1	0.3
	activationfunction	discrete	-	-
	output	discrete	-	-
	momentum	numeric	0	0.05
	number.of.layers	integer	2	4
	units	integer	32	64
ranger				
(Random forest)	mtry	integer	$\sqrt{p}/3$	p
rpart				
(CART)	minsplit	integer	20	25
	minbucket	integer	5	10
	cp	numeric	0.01	0.1
	maxcompete	integer	3	4
	maxsurrogate	integer	4	5
	usesurrogate	discrete	-	-
	surrogatestyle	discrete	-	-
	maxdepth	integer	5	15
xgboost				
(gradient-boosted trees)	nrounds	integer	10	20
	max_depth	integer	3	5
	eta	numeric	0.01	0.1
	subsample	numeric	0.5	0.9
	min_child_weight	integer	10	20
	colsample_bytree	numeric	0.5	0.9

6 Model output

The following is an example of the summary of the final ensemble model. The example down below shows the results for the potential distribution ensemble model for *Pinus sylvestris*.

```
## Species: Pinus_sylvestris
## Distribution: Potential
##
## Call:
## stats::glm(formula = f, family = "binomial", data = getTaskData(.task,
##   .subset), weights = .weights, model = FALSE)
##
## Deviance Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.8425  -0.3491   0.1860   0.2345   2.6774
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)   -3.56122    0.01080  -329.62  <2e-16 ***
## classif.ranger  6.02267    0.03285  183.33  <2e-16 ***
## classif.xgboost 1.35539    0.02918   46.44  <2e-16 ***
## classif.glmnet  0.24015    0.02174   11.05  <2e-16 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## (Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)
##
##      Null deviance: 780683  on 563170  degrees of freedom
## Residual deviance: 323051  on 563167  degrees of freedom
## AIC: 323059
##
## Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6
```

All algorithms are very significant predictors for the response variable (column $Pr(>|z|)$), while from the coefficient estimate values we infer that predictions coming from Random forest have, for this specific case, the highest weight in the final predictions of the meta-learner, followed by GLM with Lasso and finally GBT.

7 Variable importance per base model

Feature importance for the ensemble model is not available in the classical way: as seen in section 6, the predictors of the ensemble model are actually the predictions of the component models. To capture to what extent the three component models used different parts of the available feature space and the agreement between them, we compared the variable importance for each component model for each species and distribution.

Figure S4: Relative importance of the 10 most important variables across the three component models for **potential** distribution of *A. alba*, *C. sativa*, *C. avellana*, *F. sylvatica*

Figure S5: Relative importance of the 10 most important variables across the three component models for potential distribution of *O. europaea*, *P. abies*, *P. halepensis*, *P. nigra*

Figure S6: Relative importance of the 10 most important variables across the three component models for potential distribution of *P. pinea*, *P. sylvestris*, *P. avium*, *Q. cerris*

Figure S7: Relative importance of the 10 most important variables across the three component models for potential distribution of *Q. ilex*, *Q. robur*, *Q. suber*, *S. caprea*

Figure S8: Relative importance of the 10 most important variables across the three component models for realized distribution of *A. alba*, *C. sativa*, *C. avellana*, *F. sylvatica*

Figure S9: Relative importance of the 10 most important variables across the three component models for realized distribution of *O. europaea*, *P. abies*, *P. halepensis*, *P. nigra*

Figure S10: Relative importance of the 10 most important variables across the three component models for realized distribution of *P. pinea*, *P. sylvestris*, *P. avium*, *Q. cerris*

Figure S11: Relative importance of the 10 most important variables across the three component models for realized distribution of *Q. ilex*, *Q. robur*, *Q. suber*, *S. caprea*

8 Performance metrics per model and species

Table S4 and S5 show the performances achieved by component models and the ensemble model for each target species and distribution task.

Table S4: Average logloss and R^2_{logloss} for the component learners and the ensemble model. Random logloss values are dependent on presence-absence ratio in the species dataset and are here used as a baseline for predictive performances comparison.

Species	Distribution	Logloss					R^2_{logloss}			
		GBT	GLM	RF	EML	Random	GBT	GLM	RF	EML
<i>A. alba</i>	Potential	0.058	0.107	0.063	0.048	0.381	0.85	0.72	0.83	0.87
<i>C. sativa</i>	Potential	0.102	0.129	0.099	0.071	0.318	0.68	0.59	0.69	0.78
<i>C. avellana</i>	Potential	0.052	0.080	0.072	0.045	0.488	0.89	0.84	0.85	0.91
<i>F. sylvatica</i>	Potential	0.060	0.141	0.065	0.046	0.664	0.91	0.79	0.90	0.93
<i>O. europaea</i>	Potential	0.004	0.005	0.006	0.004	0.072	0.94	0.93	0.92	0.94
<i>P. abies</i>	Potential	0.127	0.176	0.118	0.112	0.693	0.82	0.75	0.83	0.84
<i>P. halepensis</i>	Potential	0.025	0.027	0.029	0.018	0.292	0.91	0.91	0.90	0.94
<i>P. nigra</i>	Potential	0.097	0.120	0.119	0.085	0.226	0.57	0.47	0.47	0.62
<i>P. pinea</i>	Potential	0.028	0.029	0.035	0.020	0.168	0.83	0.83	0.79	0.88
<i>P. sylvestris</i>	Potential	0.310	0.478	0.295	0.287	0.693	0.55	0.31	0.57	0.59
<i>P. avium</i>	Potential	0.043	0.101	0.067	0.037	0.336	0.87	0.70	0.80	0.89
<i>Q. cerris</i>	Potential	0.025	0.031	0.025	0.012	0.128	0.80	0.76	0.80	0.91
<i>Q. ilex</i>	Potential	0.068	0.094	0.071	0.055	0.276	0.75	0.66	0.74	0.80
<i>Q. robur</i>	Potential	0.058	0.096	0.071	0.044	0.647	0.91	0.85	0.89	0.93
<i>Q. suber</i>	Potential	0.005	0.010	0.009	0.006	0.126	0.96	0.92	0.93	0.95
<i>S. caprea</i>	Potential	0.053	0.062	0.083	0.050	0.654	0.92	0.91	0.87	0.92
<i>A. alba</i>	Realized	0.030	0.036	0.039	0.033	0.243	0.88	0.85	0.84	0.86
<i>C. sativa</i>	Realized	0.055	0.056	0.055	0.047	0.209	0.74	0.73	0.74	0.78
<i>C. avellana</i>	Realized	0.032	0.038	0.045	0.034	0.217	0.85	0.82	0.79	0.84
<i>F. sylvatica</i>	Realized	0.047	0.063	0.057	0.050	0.526	0.91	0.88	0.89	0.90
<i>O. europaea</i>	Realized	0.007	0.005	0.011	0.007	0.050	0.86	0.90	0.78	0.86
<i>P. abies</i>	Realized	0.097	0.144	0.105	0.101	0.657	0.85	0.78	0.84	0.85
<i>P. halepensis</i>	Realized	0.016	0.018	0.023	0.015	0.221	0.93	0.92	0.90	0.93
<i>P. nigra</i>	Realized	0.091	0.071	0.072	0.061	0.182	0.50	0.61	0.60	0.66
<i>P. pinea</i>	Realized	0.021	0.016	0.027	0.016	0.125	0.83	0.87	0.78	0.87
<i>P. sylvestris</i>	Realized	0.224	0.316	0.224	0.215	0.653	0.66	0.52	0.66	0.67
<i>P. avium</i>	Realized	0.032	0.038	0.043	0.033	0.162	0.80	0.77	0.73	0.80
<i>Q. cerris</i>	Realized	0.014	0.012	0.018	0.011	0.093	0.85	0.87	0.81	0.88
<i>Q. ilex</i>	Realized	0.041	0.045	0.047	0.036	0.209	0.80	0.78	0.78	0.83
<i>Q. robur</i>	Realized	0.050	0.064	0.064	0.051	0.423	0.88	0.85	0.85	0.88
<i>Q. suber</i>	Realized	0.005	0.005	0.009	0.005	0.099	0.95	0.95	0.91	0.95
<i>S. caprea</i>	Realized	0.043	0.058	0.059	0.046	0.318	0.86	0.82	0.81	0.86

Table S5: Average AUC and TSS for the component learners and the ensemble model.

Species	Distribution	AUC				TSS			
		GBT	GLM	RF	EML	GBT	GLM	RF	EML
<i>A. alba</i>	Potential	1.00	0.98	1.00	1.00	0.89	0.78	0.87	0.92
<i>C. sativa</i>	Potential	0.99	0.96	0.99	0.99	0.75	0.64	0.71	0.82
<i>C. avellana</i>	Potential	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	0.94	0.90	0.93	0.95
<i>F. sylvatica</i>	Potential	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	0.96	0.88	0.96	0.97
<i>O. europaea</i>	Potential	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.95	0.94	0.93	0.95
<i>P. abies</i>	Potential	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.90	0.86	0.92	0.92
<i>P. halepensis</i>	Potential	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.94	0.94	0.92	0.96
<i>P. nigra</i>	Potential	0.97	0.93	0.97	0.97	0.54	0.44	0.56	0.66
<i>P. pinea</i>	Potential	1.00	0.99	0.99	1.00	0.85	0.82	0.81	0.90
<i>P. sylvestris</i>	Potential	0.94	0.85	0.95	0.95	0.70	0.53	0.73	0.73
<i>P. avium</i>	Potential	1.00	0.98	0.99	1.00	0.90	0.76	0.86	0.93
<i>Q. cerris</i>	Potential	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.82	0.75	0.76	0.93
<i>Q. ilex</i>	Potential	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.78	0.66	0.78	0.83
<i>Q. robur</i>	Potential	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	0.96	0.93	0.95	0.97
<i>Q. suber</i>	Potential	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.97	0.94	0.95	0.97
<i>S. caprea</i>	Potential	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.96	0.95	0.95	0.97
<i>A. alba</i>	Realized	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.88	0.88	0.84	0.90
<i>C. sativa</i>	Realized	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.71	0.73	0.67	0.80
<i>C. avellana</i>	Realized	1.00	0.99	0.99	1.00	0.85	0.85	0.81	0.87
<i>F. sylvatica</i>	Realized	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.94	0.93	0.94	0.95
<i>O. europaea</i>	Realized	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.82	0.87	0.76	0.88
<i>P. abies</i>	Realized	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.91	0.88	0.91	0.92
<i>P. halepensis</i>	Realized	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.94	0.94	0.91	0.95
<i>P. nigra</i>	Realized	0.97	0.97	0.98	0.98	0.54	0.56	0.55	0.69
<i>P. pinea</i>	Realized	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.82	0.87	0.79	0.89
<i>P. sylvestris</i>	Realized	0.97	0.93	0.97	0.97	0.76	0.68	0.77	0.79
<i>P. avium</i>	Realized	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.76	0.77	0.73	0.82
<i>Q. cerris</i>	Realized	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.84	0.88	0.79	0.90
<i>Q. ilex</i>	Realized	0.99	0.99	0.99	1.00	0.79	0.78	0.75	0.85
<i>Q. robur</i>	Realized	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	0.92	0.91	0.90	0.93
<i>Q. suber</i>	Realized	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.94	0.96	0.89	0.96
<i>S. caprea</i>	Realized	1.00	0.99	0.99	1.00	0.88	0.86	0.87	0.90

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